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INFLUENCE OF MEDICINAL STEVIA TEA IN FUNCTIONAL NUTRITION

Najmitdinova Guljahon Komiljon kizi

Fergana Polytechnic Institute, Faculty of Chemical Technology, Assistant, Department of Food Technology

Annotation. For the proper organization of a healthy lifestyle and ensuring stable health of the population of Uzbekistan, an urgent task is the use of medicinal, medicinal and economically effective plants acclimatized in local conditions.

Key words: stevia, honeysuckle, stevizoite, grass, tea

ВЛИЯНИЕ ЛЕКАРСТВЕННОГО ЧАЯ СТЕВИИ В ФУНКЦИОНАЛЬНОМ ПИТАНИИ

Нажмитдинова Гулжахон Комилжон кизи

Ферганский политехнический институт, химико-технологический факультет, ассистент кафедры пищевой технологии

Аннотация. Для правильной организации здорового образа жизни и обеспечения стабильного здоровья населения Узбекистана актуальной задачей является использование лекарственных, целебных и хозяйственно эффективных растений, акклиматизированных в местных условиях.

Ключевые слова: стевия, медовая трава, стевизоит, трава, чай

Introduction

We have set ourselves the goal of planting and growing a new type of stevia plant in our country and developing innovative technologies for localization and practical use in patients with diabetes. Stevia is a perennial plant belonging to the Asteraceae family. Among the one hundred and fifty varieties of this plant known in our time, there are herbaceous and shrubby specimens. All of them differ from each other in many ways - in particular, in their composition and appearance. Humanity has known about the healing properties of stevia since ancient times. On the territory of modern Brazil and Paraguay, thousands of years ago, the Guarani Indian tribes lived, who actively used this unusual herb for food and medicinal purposes.

Due to its characteristic properties, stevia has played the role of a substitute for natural sugar. In addition, medicinal infusions and tinctures intended to treat a number of diseases were prepared from this plant, which has a pleasant taste. After some time, the demand for stevia began to decline, and priority was given to plants such as sugar cane, sugar beets and corn. Along with the need to produce low-carb sugars, stevia has become even more popular than before.

Purpose of the study

Since 2017, it has been planted on 0.5 hectares of arable land in the Markhamat district of the Andijan region in the conditions of Uzbekistan. The stevia plant is mainly used for various purposes from its leaves, stems and roots. In our current scientific research, we have studied the stevia plant as an innovative component of functional nutrition, and it is intended to enrich human health with macro- and micronutrients.

Research results

The results of the physicochemical analysis of the medicinal plant Stevia are presented in Table 1 below.

Results of physicochemical analysis of the medicinal plant Stevia

Table 1

№	Name	^o WI TH	gr	Amount of sugar	Refractive index	Dry matter content	ML	smell	taste	color
1	stevia	90°C	1 g	0.5	1.33	0.2	150 ml	Especially for the stevia plant	sweet	Transp arent dark yellow

Our research plans the importance of a new important component of the stevia plant in functional nutrition, the beneficial substances it contains for the body, and the production of products necessary for human health, especially effective in the prevention of diabetes. When we studied the composition of the domesticated Stevia plant, it turned out that it has the following indicators.

According to organoleptic indicators, stevia should have the following indicators.

table 2

Indicators	Description
	90°C
Temperature, °C	
Color	Transparent dark yellow
Taste	sweet
Smell	Suitable for stevia plants, no foreign odors

stevia sweetener

Table 3

1 sachet (3g) nutritional value/nutrition value per 1 sachet (3g)	
Proteins/possibly	0y/y
Oil/Grease	0y/y
Carbohydrates/carbohydrates	0y/y
Energy value/energy value	0 kcal/kcal

Results of physical and chemical analysis of various types of tea

Table 4

No	Name	OWITH	gr	Amount of sugar	Refractive index	Dry matter content	ML
95	Turan	80°C	2 g	0.2	1.33	0.1	100 ml
110	80.08	70°C	2 g	0.1	1.33	0.6	100 ml
		80°C	2 g	0.2	1.33	0.3	100 ml
		70°C	2 g	0.4	1.33	0.5	100 ml

Analytical results of organoleptic indicators of different types of tea

Table 5

Indicators	Description			
	Blue tea No. 8008	Blue tea No. 110	Green tea No. 95	Turon camel Chinese blue tea
Temperature, °C	90	80	70	60
Color	pale yellow	Medium blond	orange	orange
Taste	Slow down	Has a pleasant aftertaste	full of tea	Bittersweet
Smell	Suitable for tea, no foreign odors			

Results of the analysis of physicochemical parameters of the medicinal plant Stevia and various varieties tea

Table 6

No	Name	Stevia plant, gr.	Tea, gr.	OWITH	Amount of sugar	Refractive index	Dry matter content
1	Blue tea No. 80.08	1 g	1 g	90°C	0.1	1.33	0.5
2	Blue tea 110	1 g	1 g	80°C	0.0	1.33	0.7

3	Green tea 95	1 g	2 g	70° C	0.1	1.33	0.4
4	Turon camel Chinese turon with blue tea	1 g	2 g	60 °C	0.1	1.33	0.4

Results of the analysis of organoleptic characteristics of the medicinal plant Stevia and various varieties of tea

Table 7

Indicators	Description			
	Green tea No. 8008, Stevia	Green tea No. 110, Stevia	Green tea No. 95, stevia	Turon camel Chinese blue tea, stevia
Temperature, °C	90	80	70	60
Color	pale yellow	Medium blond	orange	orange
Taste	Slow down	it's bittersweet	it's bittersweet	Bittersweet
Smell	Suitable for tea, no foreign odors			

Useful properties and composition: Stevia Herbal tea prepared with stevia not only has excellent properties, but also brings great benefits to the human body. Due to its very effective healing properties, this drink is widely used in dietary, preventive and therapeutic menus. Stevia tea is also recommended for diabetics.

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